

D7.2 Report on Promotion Activities for the Open Calls

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Technical References

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Summary

Summary of Deliverable

The INN-PRESSME Open Calls (OC) will enable SMEs and other companies to access the operating Open Innovation Test Bed (OITB). It is composed of 16 Pilot Lines and related services, for the upscaling and commercialisation of innovative materials and products, as well as other technical and non-technical services, from feedstock conversion to end products. As a result, the OC will be used to select 12-15 “Innovation Concepts” in total, considering both first and second waves, that should move from TRL 4-5 up to TRL 6-7. The new Test Cases (TC) will have 9 months for the development of the corresponding project to a successful end.

The communication effort was shared between several partners participating in physical events and webinars other than the digital communication carried out by the Dissemination and Communication team (WP10). Thanks to the combined efforts of all partners, a total of 24 proposals were submitted, surpassing the initial target range of 12-15 proposals to be included in the project. Finally, the support activity provided by the WP7 contributors, aimed at explaining the INN-PRESSME assets and strengths for innovative projects, allowed a high-quality proposal preparation and a high number of submitted proposals in line with the assets proposed by the pilot lines.

The communication campaign was a success not only because it allowed to nearly double the maximum number of Innovation Concepts we wanted to receive, but also had strong interactions with the target stakeholder groups and the industry, helping in raising awareness on INN-PRESSME’s results, test cases and services.

Acronym Table

Acronym	Meaning
LE	Large Enterprise
OC	Open Call
OITB	Open Innovation Test Bed
PLs	Pilot Lines
SEP	Single-Entry Point
SME	Small/Medium Enterprise
TC	Test Case
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

The scope of this deliverable is to present a comprehensive overview of the communication efforts undertaken between September 2022 and August 2023, with the primary objective of promoting the Open Call (OC). The deliverable aims to showcase the results achieved through various activities implemented during this period, including in-person meetings, webinars, digital communication channels, and the interaction with the [INN-PRESSME digital platform](#).

Throughout the specified timeframe, a series of in-person meetings were organised to engage with relevant stakeholders, such as potential applicants, industry experts, and project partners. This was mainly possible by participating in international fairs and events, which gathered companies working in specific sectors close to those tackled by the INN-PRESSME project. These meetings served as valuable opportunities to establish personal connections, foster collaborations, and raise awareness about the OC. This deliverable provides insights into the number of meetings conducted, the participants involved, and the key outcomes and actions resulting from these interactions.

In addition to in-person meetings, webinars played a crucial role in expanding the reach of the communication efforts. Webinars provided a platform to disseminate information about the OC to a wider audience, regardless of geographical limitations. The main objective of the webinars was to explain the OITB procedures and OC process, answering the most common questions coming from 1to1 meetings previously organised with potential clients. This deliverable outlines the number of webinars conducted, topics covered, attendance rates, and feedback received from the participants.

Digital communication channels, such as social media platforms and a dedicated project website, were extensively utilised to maximize the project's visibility. This deliverable showcases the various strategies employed to leverage these channels effectively, including targeted advertisements, engaging content creation, videos, and regular updates on project developments. Metrics such as website traffic, social media engagement, and newsletter subscriptions are included to demonstrate the impact of these digital communication efforts.

Finally, this deliverable emphasises the interaction with the [INN-PRESSME digital platform](#), a dedicated online portal designed to facilitate communication and collaboration among project stakeholders. This digital platform served as a central hub for disseminating information related to the Pilot Lines (PLs), essential part of the communication effort to explain how to collaborate with the Consortium. This deliverable highlights the level of engagement and participation on the platform, including the number of registered users.

The content of this deliverable is summarised as follows:

Section 2 gives an overall description of the OC and the general dissemination strategy.

Section 3 provides a detailed description of the results for each dissemination activity.

Section 4 summarises the results of the dissemination efforts to promote the OC.

2 Overview of the OC

2.1 How the Open Call works

The OC aims to support applicants by offering up to 70% co-funding for their individual Innovation Concept Projects. This means that INN-PRESSME will cover 70% of the project costs, while the beneficiary will be responsible for the remaining 30%. The selected winners of the OC will receive services from INN-PRESSME partners, valued between 50,000 and 100,000 euros per project. These services include dedicated person-months for subsidy activities. The specific amount is determined during the negotiation of the Service Delivery Plan for each selected case. The demonstration service agreement compiled based on the INN-PRESSME Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement will be used to agree about the implementation.

In terms of projects submitted, the first round of the OC planned to select between 5 and 9 “Innovation Concepts.” The second round of OC had the objective of selecting approximately 6-10 projects to reach 12-15 “Innovation Concepts” in total. The funded projects will gain access to PLs equipped with cutting-edge technologies, enabling them to drive innovation in the biobased materials sector.

The purpose of the OC is evident in its two primary objectives. Firstly, it aims to provide valuable insights into the most sought-after PLs among potential customers. This information is crucial for developing the business model (Task 10.1). Secondly, the OC serves to raise awareness among potential customers regarding the capabilities and offerings of INN-PRESSME. Achieving this second objective is the primary focus of the current deliverable.

2.2 Goals and Objectives of the communication effort

The communication activities focused on explaining the Open Calls. The OC is the central objective of WP7, whose aim is to select new test cases to test INN-PRESSME’s PLs and prove their efficacy in providing useful services for customers from all over Europe.

The goal of the communication effort was to reach as many potential customers as possible to create a community of users that, in the future, can become clients of INN-PRESSME’s services.

The objectives of the communication and dissemination campaigns were:

- To explain the OITB procedures and services
- To explain the OC procedures, timeline, guidelines
- To promote the PLs description to help participants
- To create a database of potential customers
- To reach the highest possible number of potential customers (to achieve it, the communication effort has been directed through diverse media and channels).

Online communication has been mainly organised through the project’s website (<https://www.inn-pressme.eu/>) and LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/inn-pressme>). These tools have been used to explain the project’s activities and strengths used to help companies upgrading their bio-based solutions. Several posts have been prepared to explain the PLs facilities and services, and the benefits for different industry sectors. This activity was pivotal to allow participants to the OC (from now on, also customers) to understand how the PLs could be engaged in their proposals (Task 10.6).

2.3 Key messages

The two main key messages that the different communication activities have delivered to customers and people interacting with them are the following:

- How does the OITB work?

To promote people's participation, the first objective was to explain both how the OITB is organised and how it works. The OITB is a difficult concept for people not used to work with big consortia composed of research centres and innovative companies. To promote customers' participation, it was essential to explain the OITB procedures and which the entities composing it are. This message has been carried out mainly through the project website and the two webinars organised to promote the OC. Furthermore, face-to-face meetings and participation in industry fairs and international conferences were extremely helpful for explaining potential customers what the OITB is, and also answering their questions related to the internal procedure.

- How does the OC work?

Website, webinars and on-line or face-to-face meetings were the main channels to provide the first information on how the OC works. This includes how to participate, process deadlines, and the advantages related to participation. This helped in raising awareness and involving potential customers. The second step was the INN-PRESSME digital platform: it contains detailed information on PLs and all the necessary guidelines (reported as public Deliverable 7.1) and templates to participate in the OC.

2.4 Timeline of dissemination activities

The communication effort of INN-PRESSME encompassed various activities and events to promote the OC. The first round of the OC commenced on December 1, 2022, while the second round began on May 2, 2023. Preceding these dates, the main dissemination activities commenced in October 2022 with the release of a newsletter which promoted the first webinar on the OC. The subsequent newsletters in January 2023 and April 2023 continued to promote the OC (paragraph 0 includes the newsletter raw data).

To enhance awareness and facilitate interaction between the project coordinator, WP7 partners, and potential clients, two webinars were conducted prior to the respective opening dates. The first webinar took place on November 16, 2022, while the second webinar was held on April 27. The chosen dates allowed for the comprehensive description of both rounds of the OC to be presented several weeks in advance of the submission phase, thus providing the audience and potential clients with ample information. This was carried out in collaboration with partners active in Task 9.4.

In addition to online efforts, physical events such as fairs and seminars were attended by INN-PRESSME partners to further disseminate information about the project innovations and the OC. The following is a list of the events where partners actively promoted the project's activities and the OC, with a focus on gathering new potential customers:

- **PulPaper in Finland – 2022¹**
- **Tappi Nanotechnology Conference in Finland – 2022²**
- **IndTech in France – 2022³**

¹ <https://pulpandbeyond.messukeskus.com/>

² <https://www.tappi.org/>

³ <https://indtech2022.eu/>

- **Specialty Papers Europe in The Netherlands – 2022⁴**
- Conference on polymers and natural fibres in France – 2022⁵
- **Pitch Perfect Boost the EU Bioeconomy in Belgium - 2022⁶**
- **International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy in Italy - 2022⁷**
- **All4Pack in France - 2022⁸**
- **Greener Manufacturing Show in Germany - 2022⁹**
- **NewSkin Days 2023 in France¹⁰**
- **JEC World 2023 in France¹¹**
- **Luxe Pack in France – 2023¹²**
- Susnanofab final training event in Austria¹³
- **Joined webinar with the sister OITB: OC webinar: Upscale your bio-economy innovations: presentation of the OITBs OCs- 2023¹⁴**
- OITBs workshop (after EuroNano Forum) in Sweden, in June 2023¹⁵
- ICNF 2023 - 6th International Conference on Natural Fibers in Portugal- 2023¹⁶

Among these events, the ones highlighted in bold correspond to events where partners actively promoted the OC, with a specific focus on gathering new potential customers. The remaining events primarily served as platforms to promote INN-PRESSME's activities, while also providing an opportunity to promote the OC.

3 Dissemination results

The OC was conducted in two separate rounds, each of them generating a significant response from the innovation community. In the first round, a total of 8 Innovation Concepts were submitted through the INN-PRESSME digital platform, while the second round saw an even greater participation with 16 submissions. Out of these, 23 concepts were found to be eligible based on the guidelines provided to participants, as described in detail in Deliverable 7.1. The number of eligible submissions surpassed initial expectations, as the anticipated selection of projects was estimated to be around 15 Innovation Concepts, aligning with the allocated budget for this activity. Such a positive response indicates a strong interest and engagement from potential applicants, demonstrating a high level of enthusiasm in the INN-PRESSME project. The abundance of eligible concepts presents a valuable opportunity for the project team to carefully select and prioritize the most promising and impactful projects (Task 7.2). This selection process will ensure that the chosen projects effectively demonstrate the efficacy of the PLs and their ability to deliver innovative solutions in the biobased material sectors.

⁴ <https://www.specialtypaperconference.com/specialty-papers-europe>

⁵ <http://www.f-r-d.eu/seminar-on-natural-fibres-and-polymers/>

⁶ <https://www.bbeu.org/events/meet-us/meet-us-pitch-perfect-and-boost-the-european-bioeconomy-2022/>

⁷ <https://ifibwebsite.com/>

⁸ <https://www.all4pack.com/en>

⁹ <https://www.greener-manufacturing.com/>

¹⁰ <https://evenements.alpha-rlh.com/en/event/newskin-days-2023/programme>

¹¹ <https://www.jeccomposites.com/events/jec-world-2023/>

¹² <https://www.luxepack.com/>

¹³ <https://susnanofab.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://www.inn-pressme.eu/webinar-upscale-your-bioeconomy-innovations/>

¹⁵ https://mkon.nu/euro_nano_forum_2023

¹⁶ <https://www.icnf2023.fibrenamics.com/>

The response, the high number of eligible concepts, and the ongoing selection process jointly contribute to the overall success of the OC and they demonstrate the strong interest and support received from participants eager to leverage the INN-PRESSME ecosystem and its offer of cutting-edge technologies. This result is strongly connected to the dissemination and communication efforts, which is better explained in the following chapters.

3.1 Webpage Interaction Data

The first aspect of analytics to be considered is the interaction of the public with the project's webpage. The webpage serves as the initial point of contact for individuals interested in various topics related to the project, which extend beyond merely the OC. It offers a comprehensive overview of how the OITB functions, the services provided by the PLs, and additional essential information about the project. The analysis of the internal traffic of the webpage (Figure 1) provides valuable insights into how visitors navigate and engage with the content. In this deliverable, a specific focus is placed on the 20% of traffic directed to the PLs Archive. This section serves as a crucial resource for individuals seeking easily accessible information about the PLs involved in the OC. It represents the primary interaction point where visitors can explore and learn about the innovative solutions offered by INN-PRESSME.

Figure 1 Webpage internal traffic

The PLs Archive traffic highlights that this section plays a vital role in attracting and engaging visitors. The analytics indicate that a substantial portion of the audience recognizes the value of exploring the PLs and the opportunities that these present. This level of interest and interaction reflects the effectiveness of the webpage in capturing the attention of potential participants and providing them with the necessary information to assess the suitability of the PLs for their innovative ideas. The PLs Archive has become the gateway to accessible information and the initial introduction to the innovations offered by INN-PRESSME, this underscores its importance within the communication and dissemination efforts.

High interest for the OC is shown in the second image (Figure 2)

Figure 2 Webpage external traffic

81% of the traffic directed to external links goes to the INN-PRESSME digital platform, the place to participate in the OC. In there, it is possible to find the detailed information of all the PLs and services available to potential customers, other than the guidelines and templates for the participation in the OC and the submission of the Innovation Concepts. The analytics demonstrate the pivotal role of the website for the promotion of the OC.

3.2 Social Media Engagement Metrics

The aim of the OC is to reach a high number of potential clients. This means the communication effort was directed prominently to small, medium (SMEs), and large enterprises (LEs), the entities more capable to become customers after the first trial through the OC. Even though INN-PRESSME is present on different social media channels, the main one used to reach potential customers is LinkedIn, because of its easier access to find entities able to commit to fund research and development activities. The following figure (Figure 3) shows the overall performance of INN-PRESSME’s LinkedIn page between the 1st of January and the 14th of June 2023, which is the main period dedicated to the promotion of the OC.

Figure 3 Number of fans from the 1st of January to the 14th of June 2023

The [INN-PRESSME LinkedIn page](#) managed by the project team (ESCI) showed **notable activity and engagement** during the specified period. The page had 495 followers, indicating a significant number of individuals interested in the project's updates and content. Over the specified period, the audience grew by 28%, showcasing an increase in the number of fans and followers.

A total of **29 posts were shared** on the page (Figure 4), reflecting an active content strategy which aimed at sharing updates and information with the audience. The posts generated 19,972 organic impressions, representing the number of times the content was displayed to users without any paid promotion. Additionally, sponsored impressions reached 20,826, a necessary strategy to extend the reach of the posts to a wider audience. The posts reached a total of 568 people and the engagement rate stood at 3.7%. This number indicates the proportion of users who interacted with the content compared to the total reach. The content resonated well with the audience, resulting in positive engagement levels.

In terms of interactions, there were a total of **555 engagements**, encompassing various forms of engagement such as reactions, shares, comments, clicks, and video views. Reactions were recorded at 568, indicating positive feedback and engagement from the audience. The posts were shared 46 times.

The posts generated **382 clicks**, indicating that users were interested in learning more and took the initiative to explore additional information by clicking on the provided links. Moreover, the videos posted on the **LinkedIn page gathered a total of 9,802 views**, emphasizing the popularity of video content and its ability to capture the attention of the audience. The animated videos are [available here](#). These videos showcase the PLs and the partners' point of view on the project's innovations (Figure 5).

Figure 4 Example of LinkedIn post promoting the OC

Figure 5 Examples of videos promoting PLs

It is possible to analyse the different results between the general communication campaign, dedicated to the whole project, and the specific effort on the OC. The following table (Table 1) shows significant differences between posts related to the OC campaign and those not related to the OC campaign.

Total values	Posts	Impressions	Video views	Clicks	Reactions	Comments	Reposts	Engagement	Engagement rate
Non-OC campaign	23	17,432	1,139	554	450	2	37	489	7.3%
OC campaign	6	23,093	8,663	123	147	0	9	156	4.9%

Table 1 Total values non-OC campaign vs OC campaign

For posts not related to the campaign, a total of 23 posts were published, reaching a cumulative impression count of 17,432. This indicates that these posts collectively had a positive reach. The total video views for these posts amounted to 1,139, reflecting a good level of engagement with video content. The total number of clicks generated was 554, indicating a good level of user interaction with the provided links or call-to-action. Furthermore, there were 450 reactions, 2 comments, and 37 reposts, illustrating a higher level of engagement and interaction from the audience. The total engagement score for these posts was 489, and the engagement rate was 7.3%.

On the other hand, for **posts related to the campaign**, a total of 6 posts were published, resulting in a significantly higher total impression count of 23,093. This indicates that these campaign-related posts collectively had a broader reach compared to non-campaign posts. The total video views for these posts amounted to 8,663, showcasing a substantial level of engagement with video content. The total number of clicks generated was 123, suggesting a relatively lower level of user interaction with the provided links or call-to-action. Additionally, there were 147 reactions, 0 comments, and 9 reposts, meaning a moderate level of engagement and interaction from the audience. The total engagement score for these posts was 156, and the engagement rate was 4.9%.

Overall, the data reveals that **posts related to the campaign reached more people** compared, to posts not related to the campaign. The campaign-focused posts exhibited a stronger impact in terms of impressions, video consumption, and overall engagement, despite having a lower engagement rate. The availability of the total minutes watched metric for campaign-related posts indicates that video content played a significant role in capturing the audience's attention and driving engagement.

The average values per post based on the provided table (Table 2) gives insights into the performance of posts related to the campaign compared to those not related to the campaign.

Average values	Impressions	Video views	Clicks	Reactions	Comments	Reposts	Engagement	Min watched
<i>Non-OC campaign</i>	758	50	24	20	0	2	21	NA
<i>OC campaign</i>	3,849	1,444	21	25	0	2	26	261

Table 2 Average values per post non-OC campaign vs OC campaign

For posts not related to the campaign, each post received an average of 758 **impressions**, indicating a relatively smaller reach compared to campaign-related posts, which had an average of 3,849 impressions per post. This implies that campaign-related posts had a wider audience reach.

In terms of **video views**, non-campaign posts averaged 50 views per post, while campaign-related posts received an average of 1,444 views per post. This means that campaign-related posts gathered significantly higher engagement with video content.

For **clicks**, non-campaign posts generated an average of 24 clicks per post, while campaign-related posts averaged 21 clicks per post. Although the difference is slight, it suggests relatively similar levels of user interaction with the provided links.

Regarding **reactions**, non-campaign posts received an average of 20 reactions per post, whereas campaign-related posts averaged 25 reactions per post. This indicates that campaign-related posts garnered a slightly higher level of audience engagement and reaction to the content.

In terms of **reposts**, non-campaign posts had an average of 2 reposts per post, while campaign-related posts received an average of 26 reposts. This indicates a significantly higher level of sharing and dissemination of campaign-related posts among the audience.

The average **engagement score** per post for non-campaign posts was 21, whereas campaign-related posts had an average engagement score of 261. This indicates that campaign-related posts achieved a substantially higher level of overall audience engagement.

In summary, based on average values per post, **campaign-related posts outperformed non-campaign posts** in terms of impressions, video views, engagement, and audience interaction. This highlights the effectiveness of the campaign in reaching a wider audience, generating higher levels of engagement, and capturing the audience's attention with compelling video content.

Raw data about the interaction with LinkedIn posts are presented in Section 0.

3.3 Webinars

Webinars have been organised as a guide for potential clients interested in participating to the OC. The webinars allowed attendees to ask questions to the persons in charge of the OC in order to fine tune the Innovation Concepts to provide a high-quality proposal. The first webinar proved to be highly effective in attracting participants and generating interest, as evidenced by the following data: a total of 39 participants, of which 22 were not part of the project.

The significant number of participants indicates that the webinar successfully **captured the attention** of a diverse audience, including individuals who were not previously familiar with the project. The fact that 22 participants were not part of the consortium demonstrates that the webinar effectively reached and engaged individuals beyond the existing project network.

Webinars provide a unique platform for sharing information, facilitating communication, and fostering engagement. The interactive nature of webinars **allows attendees to actively participate**, ask questions, and gain a deeper understanding of the OC and its objectives. The fact that also INN-PRESSME's partners have participated is a positive result because the OC could also be better explained to the internal stakeholders in order to involve everyone on WP7 activities. Moreover, the presence of 22 participants who were not part of the project proves the webinar's ability to extend the reach and impact of the OC beyond the project's existing network. This suggests that the webinar effectively reached and engaged a broader audience, increasing the potential for attracting innovative and diverse project proposals.

Finally, the desired effect was to reach people interested in the OC coming from several different countries, not contacted by the in-person events attended during 2022 and 2023. This is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Number of participants per countries, not including consortium members

Figure 6 shows how many people participated in the first webinar, divided into their origin country. Data from the participants part of the Consortium has not been included. The result of the webinar was to **reach several countries** not reached by in-person meetings, such as

Morocco, The Netherlands, Norway, Singapore, India, Greece and Ireland. Not all of them are eligible countries for the OC, but they are still of interest for the future development of the OITB as they are potential customers outside the borders of EU.

The second webinar has reached less participation, with 4 participants outside of the consortium out of the 18 total participants. Although this result is less remarkable than the previous one, this may be due to the previously disseminated information. People interested in the participation to the OC already had a wide amount of information in the social networks, INN-PRESSME digital platform and in the first webinar.

Overall, now the webinars are accessible to over 950 subscribers of the ESCI YouTube channel (August 2023). Table 3 presents the number of views per video.

Table 3 Views per webinar on OC

Video	Views
<i>INN-PRESSME Webinar on the OCs 16 November 2022¹⁷</i>	66
<i>Second INN-PRESSME webinar on the OCs 27 April 2023¹⁸</i>	13
<i>“Upscale your Bioeconomy Innovations” Joint Webinar 1 March 2023¹⁹</i>	13

3.4 Interaction with INN-PRESSME Digital Platform

The [INN-PRESSME digital platform](#) is the hub for the participation in the OC. Subscribers can find all the information regarding PLs, participation guidelines, and submission section. The interaction between users and the digital platform provides an idea of the efficacy of the communication effort. From the number of subscribers (Figure 7), which has increased steadily during the months of the OC, three peaks can be evaluated.

¹⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1tYKCcuL3JE>

¹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bb5G0Tx9ovE>

¹⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vwrv1zBN6bA&list=PLb8wE1rKCAQckR89-Y8uqusbBfkJSwfen&index=8>

Figure 7 Digital platform subscribers

The **first peak** can be attributed to the initial subscription of the INN-PRESSME partners who joined the digital platform to describe the available PLs and associated services. This peak occurred before the platform was made accessible to the public. During this phase, it was populated with comprehensive specifications and information about the available technologies, enabling partners to familiarize themselves with the offerings.

The **second peak** in subscriber growth occurred when the digital platform was opened for the first round of the OC. This surge in subscribers was fuelled by the promotion of the OC through various communication activities, including the first webinar and social media campaigns. These initiatives created awareness and attracted interested parties to subscribe to the digital platform.

The **third peak** in subscriber growth is linked to the opening of the second round of the OC. This peak can be seen as the culmination of the cumulative effects of the communication efforts made in the preceding months. The continuous and consistent promotion of the project and the OC resulted in a growing interest from potential stakeholders, leading to an increase in subscribers during this phase.

The overall outcome of these communication efforts is a noticeable rise in the number of subscribers, which means the establishment of the initial core community of stakeholders interested in INN-PRESSME. This community represents the first group of potential clients who have demonstrated their interest by subscribing to the digital platform. These subscribers will have the opportunity to closely follow INN-PRESSME's developments and will be involved in future advancements. The hope is that they will ultimately decide to become paying customers.

Currently, the subscriber count stands at 131, being 57 of them external to the consortium, which indicates their potential as future clients. These external subscribers confirm the expansion of the stakeholder community beyond the project's immediate network, reflecting the success of the communication efforts in attracting external interest and participation.

3.5 Email Communication Results

Overall, the email campaigns were successful in delivering the messages to the recipients, with delivered rates ranging from 92.59% to 97.73%. The opening rates varied from 40.28% to 49.23%, indicating a good level of engagement with the content. The click rates ranged from 12.16% to 20%, demonstrating that the readers found the content compelling enough to take further action. Data are listed in Table 4 and showed in Figure 8, while the raw dataset is available in chapter 0.

Table 4 Interaction with newsletters

Newsletter	Sending date	Tot Delivered	Tot opens	Tot clicked
Newsletter 4	20/10/2022	65	159	53
Newsletter 5	17/01/2023	74	127	22
OITB joint webinar - March 2023	22/02/2023	75	79	26
Newsletter 6	03/04/2023	86	98	51
Newsletter 7	03/07/2023	95	103	26
Tot		395	566	178

Figure 8 Visualization of interactions with the project newsletters

The data suggests that the **email campaigns effectively reached the intended audience** and gathered positive engagement, leading recipients to open the emails and click on the provided links. These successful campaigns played a crucial role in promoting the INN-PRESSME project and its OC, attracting interest and encouraging potential stakeholders to upscale their biomaterials through the project's offering. The project newsletters are published [here on the project website](#).

4 Conclusion

The campaigns related to the Open Call have been successful in reaching a wide audience and generating high levels of engagement. Posts related to the campaign achieved higher levels of impressions, video views, and overall engagement compared to non-campaign posts. This indicates that the campaign-focused content had a stronger impact in terms of reach and audience interaction, despite having a lower engagement rate. The use of video content in the campaign proved to be particularly effective in capturing the audience's attention and driving engagement. The analytics on the PLs archive in the project's site indicate that a substantial portion of the audience recognizes the value of exploring the PLs and the opportunities they present. Furthermore, the PLs archive serves as a gateway to accessible information and an initial introduction to the innovations offered by INN-PRESSME, underscoring its importance within the communication and dissemination efforts.

The webinars have been an essential component of the communication effort, providing a **unique platform for sharing information** and fostering engagement. The first webinar, in particular, attracted a significant number of participants, including both external stakeholders and INN-PRESSME partners. However, the second webinar saw a relatively lower participation rate, which could be attributed to the already disseminated information and the audience's familiarity with the Open Call through previous communication efforts. Nonetheless, the webinars have been accessible to over 950 subscribers to ESCI YouTube channel, indicating their potential in reaching a broader audience and disseminating project-related information.

As a result of these communication efforts, **the number of subscribers to INN-PRESSME digital platform has notably increased**, creating the first core community of stakeholders centred around INN-PRESSME. This community represents potential clients who have demonstrated their interest by subscribing to the digital platform. These subscribers will continue to be engaged with INN-PRESSME's developments and innovations, with the hope that they will ultimately decide to become paying customers. Currently, the subscriber count stands at 131, with 57 of them being external to the consortium, which means the expansion of the stakeholder community beyond the project's immediate network.

The communication efforts have proven to be effective in promoting the INN-PRESSME project and its Open Call, attracting interest, engaging stakeholders, and increasing the subscriber base. The success of the campaigns and webinars, together with webpage analytics, demonstrate the project's ability to reach a diverse audience and foster meaningful interactions with potential clients, industry players and stakeholders. These positive outcomes show a bright future for INN-PRESSME and its endeavours in the field of biomaterials and sustainable innovation.

5 Annex – Raw data communication

5.1 LinkedIn raw data

Date	Post title	Impres sions	Views	Clic ks	CTR	Re act ion s	C o m p o s t s	R e p o s t s	Enga gem ent rate
04/01/ 2023	We wish all the best for the New Year 2023! 🎉 This is going to be an exciting & busy year for INN-PRESSME! Don't miss out your opportunity to participate in our #OpenCall! 📄 https://lnkd.in/en_6Xfkt #biomaterials #nanomaterials #biobased #upscaling #pilotlines #OITB	444	120	8	1.8 %	13	0	0	4.7%
13/01/ 2023	Supporting the end of single-use plastics by 2040, reusable packaging should be developed. 📄 Buddie-Pack - contribution to the EU plastics strategy - is a European project working on a systemic approach for the large-scale deployment of reusable packaging in society. 🌍 👁 Interested in learning more? IPC Centre Technique Industriel de la Plasturgie et des Composites's Research team offers an exclusive webinar in French that will present BUDDIE-PACK and three other collaborative research projects: CIMPA - INN-PRESSME - FF2S 📅 31 January 2023 🕒 11 am Registration: https://hubs.li/Q01w_6Sn0 #packaging #reusable #recycling #biomaterials	211	-	6	2.8 %	5	0	0	5.2%
17/01/ 2023	Surface Treatment Concept – How biomaterial layers make packaging more sustainable.	1,087	585	20	1.8 %	38	0	2	5.5%
19/01/ 2023	INN-PRESSME project newsletter - Inn-Pressme	566	-	18	3.2 %	19	0	2	6.9%
24/01/ 2023	Only 7 Days Left! Don't miss to apply for our #OpenCall! Deadline for submission is 30 January 2023. 📄 https://lnkd.in/en_6Xfkt #Biomaterials #Nanomaterials #PilotLines #Upscaling #CircularEconomy	1,226	-	40	3.2 %	27	0	2	5.5%

30/01/2023	🔔 LAST DAY to submit your #application for the 1st INN-PRESSME #OpenCall! We are looking forward receiving your application & helping your company #scalingup your #innovative & #novel products based on #biomaterials. Further information, application form & link to submission is available on our website: 🌐 https://lnkd.in/en_6Xfkt #PilotLines #biobased #nanomaterials #innovations #sustainability	997	-	15	1,50 %	18	0	5	3.8%
16/02/2023	The Open Innovation Test Beds (OITBs) are true collaborative ecosystems that offer technological and market-oriented services covering the complete value chain. Four OITBs (BIOMAC, INN-PRESSME, BIOMAT Project, Bionanopolys) have recently launched their Open Calls, granting you the unique opportunity to upscale your ideas and take your bionanomaterial project from lab stage to industrial prototype. To this end, your company can benefit from the services of the available pilot lines and service hubs to cover your entire value chain. Check out the agenda & register to our webinar: https://lnkd.in/e5_a55R5 #OITB #OpenCall #Biomaterials #Nanomaterials #PilotLines #Upscaling #CircularEconomy #Industry #Sustainability	397	-	13	3.3 %	22	0	3	9.6%
21/02/2023	📌 Upscale your bioeconomy innovations for becoming more sustainable! On 01 March 2023, four Open Innovation Test Beds present opportunities to test their pilots and how to apply for their Open Calls. Further information and registration: 🌐 https://lnkd.in/e5_a55R5 #Upscale #PilotLine #Innovations #Bioeconomy #Biomaterials #Nanomaterials #OITB #OpenCall	570	-	6	1.1 %	20	0	2	4.9%
23/02/2023	Establishing of a Development Environment for Bio-based Particle Foams	1,334	-	43	3.2 %	32	2	1	5.9%
28/02/2023	Upscale your bioeconomy innovations Tomorrow - 1st March at 11.00 CET - will be our free workshop: 🌐 https://lnkd.in/dRgj-Ary Join us online and discover the benefits of the recently launched Open Calls of BIOMAC, BIOMAT Project, Bionanopolys and INN-PRESSME - 4 Open Innovation Test Beds (#OITBs) funded by Horizon 2020. Want to discover how you can access true collaborative ecosystems that offer technological and market-oriented services covering the complete value chain? Attend the event, organised by EUBIA European Biomass Industry Association, and don't miss this unique opportunity to boost your ideas and take your bionanomaterials developments from the lab stage to an industrial prototype. #CircularEconomy #IndustrialSymbiosis	323	-	6	1.9 %	15	0	0	6.5%

	#Biomaterials #Nanomaterials #Upscaling #Bioeconomy #OpenCall #Sustainability								
02/03/2023	Yesterday our joint workshop about "Upscale your Bioeconomy Innovations" took place. You have not been able to join? You can watch the recordings here https://lnkd.in/e9RWDXqK Find out how the Open Calls of BIOMAC, BIOMAT Project, Bionanopolys and #INNPRESSME can help your company to upscale your ideas and take your bionanomaterial project from lab stage to industrial prototype. #Bioeconomy #Biomaterials #Nanomaterials #PilotLines #Upscaling #BusinessOpportunity	290	-	4	1.4 %	17	0	0	7.2%
15/03/2023	INN-PRESSME Pilot Line 1 - Cellulose NanoFibril Production	473	947	23	4.9 %	19	0	3	9.5%
31/03/2023	Cellulose Nano Crystals – a real sustainable alternative for fossil materials.	1,115	702	25	2.2 %	22	0	1	4.3%
03/04/2023	👉 Pick up the latest issue now! 👉 Our latest #newsletter is already waiting for you. Exciting topics and #background information, including all the information on the 2nd #OpenCall EU and the latest #videos on our #pilotlines. https://lnkd.in/dXNKTCPC #biomaterials #nanomaterials #circulareconomy #sustainabledevelopment #innovation #OITB #opencall #recycling #replaceplastic #research #europe Fraunhofer Institute for Silicate Research ISC Fraunhofer ICT Aitiip Centro Tecnológico CIDETEC Polymarís Biotechnology IPC Centre Technique Industriel de la Plasturgie et des Composites CEA-List Gnanomat AIMPLAS · Technological Institute of Plastics SD Partners EU RISE Processum IRES Greenovate! Europe ESCI - European Science Communication Institute Geonardo Environmental Technologies Albéa Group PODOACTIVA European Commission European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)	557	-	13	2.3 %	16	0	2	5.6%
18/04/2023	📣 PARTICIPATE IN THE SECOND INN-PRESSME WEBINAR ON THE OPEN CALLS! Are you a SME, a Research and Technology Organisation or a large company looking for solutions to scale-up your biomaterials in the packaging, transport, energy and consumer goods sectors? Join us on 27 April 2023, to learn more about the INN-PRESSME services and discover the benefits of an Open Innovation Test Bed. The technologies and pilots developed during the INN-PRESSME project will allow winning companies to develop new nano bio-materials, produce and test new bio-based materials from bio-based feedstocks. Don't miss this opportunity	376	-	8	2.1 %	23	0	6	9.8%

	to learn more about inspiring best practices, building on the lessons learned and results of the 1st Open Call. Registration to the webinar ↗ https://lnkd.in/e2zwzX-n Our 2nd Open Call will be launched on 2 May 2023. Details about participation rules and how to prepare your successful application are available on website: https://lnkd.in/en_6Xfkt #Biomaterials #OITB #OpenCall #Webinar #UpScaling #PilotLines #Packaging #Transport #ConsumerGoods #Transport								
20/04/2023	🔗 Interested to learn more about our #OITB services? 📄 Have a look at the article published about the #INNPRESSME OITB at Innovation News Network ! For companies interested in replacing their fossil-based plastic products by #biomaterials, we highly recommend to participate in our webinar on 27 April 2023. Registration ↗ https://lnkd.in/gS_DuYST #nanomaterials #upscaling #pilots #sustainability #consumergoods #packaging #energy #transport #innovation	150	-	3	2.0 %	8	0	0	7.3%
24/04/2023	🔗 Have you registered to our 2nd webinar on the INN-PRESSME #OpenCall yet? Don't miss your opportunity to find out more about our #services for your company! Free registration ↗ https://lnkd.in/eZuJDdhF #Biomaterials #ScalingUp #Pilots #ConsumerGoods #Packaging #Innovations	482	-	23	4.8 %	22	0	1	9.5%
25/04/2023	Only 2 days left until the 2nd webinar takes place about the INN-PRESSME Open Calls! Join us online on 27 April from 10:00-11:30 CET to discover how your company can benefit from our pilot lines, our services and our Open Innovation Test Bed. The participation is free of charge. Just register here ↗ https://lnkd.in/e2zwzX-n Next week, starting on 02 May 2023, we will launch our second Open Call. Check out in the webinar your opportunities to apply! https://lnkd.in/gS_DuYST #OpenCall #Benefit #PilotLines #Services #OpenInnovationTestBed #OITB #Biomaterials #UpScaling #Sustainability	340	-	8	2.4 %	14	0	1	6.8%
27/04/2023	We just held our 2nd webinar on the INN-PRESSME #OpenCalls! You missed it? All the presentations are available on our project website: https://lnkd.in/gS_DuYST The recordings of the webinar will be published soon on our website too. On 02 May 2023, we will launch our 2nd Open Call. Stay tuned for more! #Biomaterials #UpScaling #PilotLines	325	-	52	16.0 %	18	0	0	21.5 %
27/04/2023	We are starting at 10:00 CET with our 2nd webinar on the INN-PRESSME #OpenCalls! Hurry up to reserve your spot! 📄 📄 🗣️ 🌐 https://lnkd.in/e2zwzX-n Find out how your company can apply to test your own innovative ideas in the	202	-	9	4.5 %	10	0	2	10.4 %

	#biomaterials sector and get access to the #services provided by the 16 project #pilotlines. See you soon!								
03/05/2023	INN-PRESSME Open Call Trailer	1,170	1.019	12	1.0 %	33	0	6	4.4%
09/05/2023	How Biomaterials Make Batteries More Sustainable and Replace Carbon	1,196	1.310	22	1.8 %	31	0	2	4.6%
23/05/2023	Quality improvement of bio-based coatings and nanoparticle synthesis	18,716	4.933	24	0.1 %	20	0	0	0.4%
05/06/2023	? Is your company working on novel #biobased #technologies and #products? ? Check the services that our Open Call for #testing and #upscaling your #innovations in #biomaterials at the #pilots offered by our partners VTT, Fraunhofer Institute for Silicate Research ISC, Fraunhofer ICT, IPC Centre Technique Industriel de la Plasturgie et des Composites, CEA-List, CIDETEC, Aitiip Centro Tecnológico, Polymarís Biotechnology, RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, Gnanomat and Lenkon IWNiRZ PIB! ↗ https://lnkd.in/g-5NUzVA	4,365	-	107	2.5 %	46	0	1	3.5%
06/06/2023	You want to apply to the INN-PRESSME Open Call but need more information about the procedure? ↗ https://lnkd.in/g-5NUzVA On our dedicated #OpenCall website we provide you with all the information you need: 📄 the guide for applicants, 📄 the application template and 📄 the registration form. You still have questions? Please get in direct contact with us via opencall@inn-pressme.eu! We are happy to assist you with all matters concerning your application. Application for this Open Call closes 15 June 2023! #Biomaterials #Nanomaterials #Pilots #Upscaling #Innovation #Sustainability VTT Fraunhofer Institute for Silicate Research ISC Fraunhofer ICT IPC Centre Technique Industriel de la Plasturgie et des Composites CEA-List CIDETEC Aitiip Centro Tecnológico Polymarís Biotechnology RISE Research Institutes of Sweden Gnanomat Lenkon IWNiRZ PIB	1,020	-	134	13.1 %	11	0	0	14.2 %
07/06/2023	Companies working on #biomaterials can apply with their #innovation #concepts to the INN-PRESSME #OpenCall and benefit from our #pilot scale trials. Open call winners have free access to state-of-the-art #pilotlines. Visit our dedicated website to find out more! ↗ https://lnkd.in/g-5NUzVA Application deadline is 15 June 2023! #recycling #packaging #solutions #technologies #upscaling	892	-	13	1.5 %	31	0	0	4.9%
13/06/2023	! ONLY 24 hours left to apply for the INN-PRESSME #OpenCall! Don't forget to send your application for testing our #cuttingedge #technologies on	357	-	7	2.0 %	17	0	3	7.6%

	https://lnkd.in/g-5NUzVA #Biomaterials! #PilotLines #Testing #Upscaling #Nanomaterial #Sustainability								
06/09/2023	INN-PRESSME - Ulla Forsström explains Open Call benefits	506	186	9	1.8 %	17	0	1	5.3%
01/11/2023	🔗 Do you want to know how INN-PRESSME supports your #innovations through our #OpenCall? 📄 Our coordinator Ulla Forsström from VTT explains in this Spotlight article how #recyclable #biomaterials can transform the #industry and how industrial partners can benefit from our knowledge gained during the project. Check out what is in for your company and apply to our Open Call. Su-bmission Deadline is 31 January 2023! #Upscaling #PilotLines #Sustainability	838	-	6	0.7 %	13	0	0	2.3%

5.2 Newsletter raw data

Campaign Name	Sending date	Subject	Recipients	No n delivered	Hard bounces	Soft bounces	Non delivered rate	Delivered	Total opens	Opened	Trackable open rate	Total clicked	Clicked	Click rate	Click-to-Open rate	Delivered rate
<i>Newsletter 4</i>	20/10/2022	Get ready for the INN-PRESSME Open Calls to use our pilots and services!	70	5	2	3	7.14 %	65	159	30	49.18 %	53	13	20 %	43.33 %	92.86 %
<i>Newsletter 5</i>	17/01/2023	Apply now to test the INN-PRESSME pilots and upscale your biomaterials	77	3	1	2	3.90 %	74	127	32	49.23 %	22	9	12.16 %	28.13 %	96.10 %
<i>OITB joint webinar - March 2023</i>	22/02/2023	Join our webinar: Upscale Your Bioeconomy Innovations - Wednesday March 1st	81	6	0	6	7.41 %	75	79	29	40.28 %	26	13	17.33 %	44.83 %	92.59 %
<i>Newsletter 6</i>	03/04/2023	Don't miss the second open call to scale up your biomaterials with INN-PRESSME.	88	2	0	2	2.27 %	86	98	35	44.30 %	51	13	15.12 %	37.14 %	97.73 %
<i>Newsletter 7</i>	03/07/2023	Scaling-up your sustainable biomaterials and accelerating innovation	98	3	0	3	3.06 %	95	103	39	43.33 %	26	13	13.68 %	33.33 %	96.94 %

